

Description of files included in Zenodo repository

NOTE: here, *adVMP* and *aDVMC* are used interchangeably. Additionally, *EPIC2* = *SWEPIC1*, *EPIC3* = *SWEPIC2*, *EPIC4* = *SWEPIC3*.

adVMP/

This folder contains all the files derived from the aDVMC discovery.

- *all_advmps.csv*: contains the list of all probes that were selected as differentially variable and methylated in at least one dataset
- *full_adVMP_description.csv*: statistics on all aDVMCs, in all SWEPIC cohorts. Equivalent to Suppl. Table 2.
- *union_cpgs.csv*: list of the aDVMCs, defined as differentially variable and methylated probes found in at least two SWEPIC cohorts.

adVMP_crossvalidation_4fold/

This folder contains all the files derived from the aDVMC cross-validation scheme.

- SWEPIC{i}/
 - Fold{j}/
 - *adVMP_right.csv*: full statistics on all probes, q is the FDR corrected p-value of the Bartlett test, diffV is the difference in variance between the adenoma and non-adenoma group ($\text{diffV} > 0$ means more variability in the adenoma group), ttest_p is the p-value of the t-test for differential methylation
 - *sample_test_set.csv*: list of specimens in the test fold
 - *sample_train.set_csv*: list of specimens in the train fold

adVMP_link_clinical/

This folder contains the results of the analysis linking clinical characteristics with the beta-value at aDVMC sites. We model the beta value as a multivariate GLM with Gamma link function, using all clinical characteristics as exogenous variables and beta values at the site as the endogenous variable.

- SWEPIC{i}/
 - *{clinical_characteristic}.csv*: each of these files contain the results of the analysis to link clinical characteristics with methylation at aDVMC sites. For each clinical characteristic, for each aDVMC, we report the results of the GLM model, notably the coefficient, the std error, the Z-score, p-value, CI, and FDR q value of significance.

auxiliary/

This folder contains miscellaneous information needed for the analysis

- *Colon_highlevel_ref.csv*: this file originates from “Zhu T, Liu J, Beck S, Pan S, Capper D, Lechner M, et al. A pan-tissue DNA methylation atlas enables in silico decomposition of human tissue methylomes at cell-type resolution. *Nat Methods*. 2022;19:296–306.”. This is the reference atlas developed for colon, used for the deconvolution algorithm, EpiSCORE.
- *full_background_probes.csv*: this contains the full list of probes that passed QC for SWEPIC1-3.

- *horvath_age.csv*: the age computed using the Horvath clock
- *horvath_cpg.csv*: the list of CpG used by the Horvath clock, with the associated coefficient, and median value in the dataset. Used to estimate the age.
- *sketchy_probe_list_450k.csv*: historically unreliable probes, as described in <https://life-epigenetics-methylcheck.readthedocs-hosted.com/en/latest/docs/filtering-probes.html>.
- *sketchy_probe_list_EPIC.csv*: historically unreliable probes, as described in <https://life-epigenetics-methylcheck.readthedocs-hosted.com/en/latest/docs/filtering-probes.html>.

clinical/

This folder contains all the clinical information used in the paper for each patient included in the SWEPIC cohort.

- *targets.csv*: the information about the presence of a polyp, categorized as adenomatous or sessile serrated, in each region assessed (any, right, left, rectum)
- *sample_origin_wbatch.csv*: the link between the specimen number, the patient of origin, the location of the sample (cecum or sigmoid), and the associated batch (if not profiled, will be left blank).
- *institution_information.csv*: the link between the patient ID and the institution the sample was taken in.
- *cleaned_clinical_reduced_diet.csv*: all clinical information used in the paper
 - gender: 1=F, 0=M;
 - age at visit in years;
 - BMI;
 - fam.hist.colorec ca (3cat)=history of colorectal cancer in the family, 0=None, 1=close relative, 2=further relative;
 - ATP III: abdominal obesity;
 - ATP III elevated triglycerides;
 - ATP III low HDL, ATP III hypertension;
 - ATP III – diabetes/hyperglycaemia;
 - Diabetes (overall);
 - ATP III Nr. fulfilled;
 - Metabolic syndrome;
 - Baby aspirin ≥ 2 years (overall);
 - Baby aspirin ≥ 5 years (overall);
 - Analgesic ≥ 2 years (overall);
 - Analgesic ≥ 5 years (overall);
 - Baby aspirin or analgesic ≥ 2 years;
 - Baby aspirin or analgesic ≥ 5 years;
 - Ever smoked cigarettes;
 - Past smoked cigarettes;
 - Pack years = a measure of how many pack a day during a year an individual has smoked
 - Smoking ≥ 20 years;
 - Smoking ≥ 30 years;
 - Curr. nr. cigarettes/day
 - Past nr. cigarettes/day

- inflammatory_n;
- anti-inflammatory_n;
- western_n;
- prudent_n;
- polyps_total_nr;
- polyps_total_size: sum of the size of all discovered polyps;
- polyps_right_nr;
- size_py_rght;
- Polyp Location;

EpiSCORE_results/

This folder contains the results of the deconvolution of the methylation data using the EpiSCORE algorithm using a reference atlas for the colon.

- epic4_estimates.csv: estimates for all SWEPIC3 patients.
- epic123_estimates.csv: estimates for all patients of SWEPIC1 and SWEPIC2.

illumina_manifests/

This folder contains a copy of the illumina manifests for different technologies

- *GPL13534_HumanMethylation450_15017482_v.1.1.csv*: the manifest for Illumina 450k.
- *GPL21145_MethylationEPIC_15073387_v-1-0.csv.gz*: the manifest for Illumina EPIC.

NIH_Epigenomics_Roadmap/

This folder contains the files used and produced by the analysis linking the Roadmap Epigenomics Consortium annotated states in colonic mucosa (more detail in Roadmap Epigenomics Consortium, Kundaje A, Meuleman W, Ernst J, Bilenky M, Yen A, et al. Integrative analysis of 111 reference human epigenomes. Nature. 2015;518:317–30.).

- *E075_15_coreMarks_dense.bed.gz*: the Roadmap epigenomics consortium annotated states in the colonic mucosa.
- *EPIC_to_state_mapping.csv*: for each probe in the EPIC manifest, we map to the corresponding state if annotated in the Roadmap epigenomics consortium file

RNAseq/

This folder contains the plate layout used for the RNAseq analysis

- *batch_layout.csv*: plate layout for the analyzed samples for the RNAseq analysis

variable_probes/

This folder contains the probes that are the most variable probes in healthy tissue for the comparison with random probes

- *union_cpgs_5_pct_most_variable_onlyhealthy.csv*: for each SWEPIC dataset, we compute the std of probes in tissue of patients with no polyps at colonoscopy and select the 5% most variable; these are the unique probes selected in at least one dataset.
- *union_cpgs_5_pct_most_variable_onlyhealthy.csv*: for each SWEPIC dataset, we compute the std of probes in tissue of all patients and select the 5% most variable; these are the unique probes selected in at least one dataset.